

TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO OLDER LEARNERS

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Abstract: The field of older adult education is still under-researched, with many terminological ambiguities, clichés, and prejudices. The training of educators for older adults and the specific area of older adult English as a foreign language (EFL) teacher education are particularly rare. Many factors can influence the teaching performance of EFL teachers working with older adults and how this performance is perceived. This study examined pre-service (presumably inexperienced U3A EFL teachers) and in-service teachers (experienced U3A EFL teachers) who were teaching EFL to selected older adults (aged from 64 to 75 years) at the Karkonosze University of Applied Sciences in Jelenia Gora, Poland, U3A. Their teaching performance factors were analyzed. By utilizing a critical foreign language pedagogy and a strengths-based approach inspired by positive psychology, the research emphasized the role of general teaching experience and/or age-targeted teaching experience. This led to the validation of desirable teaching performance factors as factors that defined U3A EFL teaching performance as successful and positively evaluated by the given older adult learners, albeit on a small scale.

Key words: EFL, Course book, activation program, backgrounds, ventilation, learning modalities

Introduction

Based on a qualitative comparative exploratory study, this paper analyzes how to approach teaching EFL to older adult learners at a University of the Third Age (U3A). It aimed to design a desirable U3A EFL teaching performance and to

validate it on a small scale. The study primarily focused on the role of teaching experience and official educational study path. A comparison was made between the teaching performance of pre-service (presumably non-experienced U3A EFL teachers) and in-service teachers (experienced U3A EFL teachers) at one selected U3A EFL course and its attendees (aged 64 to 75 years). The study revealed that positively perceived (and successful) teaching performance needs to involve, among others, the following factors: establishing a friendly atmosphere, adjusting materials to the target group and the tempo, becoming partners with learners, and being sensitive to their limitations and barriers and respectful to their wishes and needs. However, within the researched countries, pre-service teachers are not being prepared to teach older adults in their formal education path. The teachers' experience plays a significant role in the ability to adapt and adjust, however, the enjoyment of foreign language learning perceived by older adults is universal. This enjoyment was perceived in both variants, i.e. at pre-service as well as in-service teachers' teaching performance.

The complex topic of 'foreign language geragogy,' which refers to the specialized field of teaching foreign languages to older adults (as explored in works by Ramírez-Gómez in 2015, 2016a, 2016b, and 2019), and the education of teachers in this field was addressed using a strengths-based approach. The aim was to validate desirable teaching performance in foreign language education from four distinct perspectives. While the qualitative comparative exploratory study used cannot provide definitive conclusions, the research aimed to advance geragogy research and provide practical assistance for geragogy practitioners. The purpose was to make English as a foreign language (EFL) teaching and teacher training, or 'teacher education' (Kliesch et al., 2017), more sensitive to the age factor, as Withnall (2009) refers to it as 'tutor training.'

This focus on older adults is particularly relevant because the population structure within Western society has changed, with an increasing number of older adults, increased life expectancy, and improved quality of life in later years.

Consequently, the expectations of older adults have also changed (Petikova & Čornačičová, 2004). Life no longer simply ends with accepting its finality, as Erikson's concept of 'existential identity' suggests (see, for example, Goleman, 1988, p. 1). Instead, life continues with aspirations for social integration and engaging in meaningful conversations (Hubenthal, 2004). Adults are re-entering the educational process, leading to increasing opportunities to expand 'learning careers' (Gallacher et al., 2002) into later life. The establishment of organizations supporting this growth, such as AIUTA founded in 1975, ESREA founded in 1991, and ELOA founded in 2010 (see, for example, Tøsse, 2016), highlights this trend. Today, we see Universities of the Third Age (U3A), Academies of the Third Age, libraries, activation programs in care homes, and other initiatives (Adamec & Kryštof, 2011; Čornačičová, 1998) providing opportunities for older adults to pursue their educational goals informally, locally, globally (e.g., online), autonomously or collectively. These educational opportunities are both institutionalized and tied to local communities. The U3A investigated in this research represents one of many practical opportunities for expanding learning careers into older adulthood.

The world is changing, and with it, the demographics of language learners. Older adults, fueled by a desire for personal enrichment, professional advancement, and the pursuit of cognitive well-being, are increasingly seeking English language instruction. However, teaching English to older learners presents unique challenges that require a departure from traditional pedagogical approaches. Recognizing and addressing these challenges is crucial for creating an engaging and effective learning environment for this growing demographic.

While older learners bring a wealth of life experience and knowledge to the classroom, they also present unique learning needs that teachers must understand and address. Older adults may struggle with memory retention, requiring teachers to employ strategies that reinforce learning through repetition and active recall.

Spaced repetition, using various learning modalities like visual aids, auditory cues, and kinesthetic activities, can enhance memory retention.

Many older learners may feel intimidated by technology, leading to a reluctance to embrace online resources. Introducing technology gradually, starting with familiar platforms and progressively introducing new tools, is key. Teachers should demonstrate the benefits of technology for language learning, emphasizing its potential for enhancing communication, accessing authentic materials, and engaging in interactive exercises. Older adults often learn at a slower pace than younger learners. Teachers should adjust their teaching style to allow for more time for processing information, providing opportunities for repetition, and encouraging collaborative learning.

A comfortable and supportive classroom environment is essential for older learners. This includes adequate lighting, ventilation, and seating arrangements that accommodate individual needs. Teachers should also be sensitive to potential health concerns like hearing loss or vision impairment, providing accommodations as necessary. The demands of family and work can make it challenging for older learners to maintain motivation and focus. Teachers can foster engagement by creating relevant and engaging activities, using a variety of teaching methods, and incorporating real-world scenarios into language practice.

A thorough needs analysis is essential to understand the specific goals, learning preferences, and background knowledge of each student. This information will guide the selection of appropriate learning materials, instructional strategies, and assessment tools. Finding suitable course books for older learners can be difficult. Many adult-oriented course books might contain content that is too juvenile or simplistic. Teachers should seek out materials that address the needs and interests of older learners, including topics related to health, travel, technology, or cultural awareness. Using real-world materials like news articles, documentaries, TED Talks, and podcasts exposes learners to authentic English, making the learning process more relevant and engaging.

Leveraging technology can enhance the learning experience for older adults. Online platforms offer opportunities for interactive exercises, vocabulary practice, grammar review, and communication with native speakers. However, teachers should ensure that technology is used strategically and does not become a barrier to learning. Collaborative learning activities encourage peer support, create opportunities for practice, and foster a sense of community among learners. Group work allows older learners to share their experiences, learn from each other, and build confidence in their language skills. Teachers should be sensitive to the diverse cultural backgrounds and experiences of older learners. They should avoid making assumptions or stereotypes and create an inclusive learning environment that values individual perspectives.

Training and professional development programs that specifically address the needs of older adult language learners are essential for equipping teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge. These programs should cover topics such as:

- * Understanding the learning characteristics of older adults
- * Adapting teaching methods and materials for this demographic
- * Incorporating technology into the classroom
- * Fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment
- * Engaging in culturally responsive teaching practices

Teaching English to older learners presents unique challenges and opportunities. By recognizing and addressing the specific needs of this population, teachers can create a stimulating and effective learning environment that empowers older adults to reach their language goals. Through a commitment to ongoing professional development, teachers can continue to refine their practices and ensure that older learners have access to the high-quality instruction they deserve.

As the world continues to evolve, the need for effective language education for older adults will only grow. By embracing innovative approaches and fostering a supportive learning environment, educators can empower older learners to

navigate the challenges of a globalized world and thrive in a diverse and interconnected society.

The research was conducted with respondents from two countries: the Czech Republic (CZ) and Poland (PL). These respondents represented both institutionalized teacher education programs and life-long learning programs/older adult education programs, specifically focusing on institutionalized U3A programs (following the French model). Although the very first U3A was established in 1973 (Vellas, 2019, pp. 19–30), marking 50 years of existence, the first attempts at developing an independent discipline addressing the unique needs of older adults within educational theory were made as early as 1978 (Słowik-Krogulec, 2019, p. 190), marking 45 years of development.

In both CZ and PL, geragogy, which is currently one of the fastest-growing subdisciplines (Tøsse, 2016, p. 127) focused on "teaching towards older people accommodating [their] normal physical, cognitive and psychological changes" (Socrates Grundtvig Organization, n.d., p. 2), has not yet fully established itself as an independent scientific field. In both countries, foreign language geragogy is discussed within health studies or educational studies, meaning it is not integrated within foreign language methodology. Table 1 lists the courses discussing older adult education and the relevant study programs. This table reflects the lack of geragogy and geragogy-focused programs in care home teacher education, highlighting the absence of qualified training for "geragogues" (Balogová & Kmetóny Gazdová, 2019, p. 40). Table 1 also illustrates the terminological ambiguity associated with the field (using terms such as gerontagogy, gerontopedagogy, gerontological education, educational work with senior citizens, or social gerontology).

Research in this field is also rare, with exceptions such as Derenowski's (2017) research on the characteristics of foreign language teachers. EFL teacher education primarily targets a very limited population, namely those between the ages of 5 and 19, with the education largely being age-specific. However, there is

no specific focus on pre-schoolers or individuals within the productive or post-productive age groups (Koutská, 2020, p. 14).

Conclusion

The research was conducted as a qualitative comparative exploratory study on a small scale. It aimed to address the complex topic of foreign language geragogy and foreign language geragogy teacher education from various perspectives. The study resulted in a description of how chosen teachers, both pre-service and in-service teachers, taught selected older adults at one U3A EFL course, and how their perspectives and perceptions differed from one another. A generalizable and potentially transferable desirable teaching performance was aimed at and validated on a small scale.

The four perspectives were researched, and therefore the recommendations are also directed toward different actors. One set of recommendations is for EFL teacher educators (specifically EFL geragogy teacher educators). The recommendation is to incorporate age-targeted instruction and teaching experience into current pre-/in-service EFL teacher education and further professional development programs.

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